

POLICY BRIEF

TOWARDS STANDARDISATION OF THE ASSESSMENT OF REUSABLE PLASTIC PACKAGING INTENDED FOR CONTACT SENSITIVE APPLICATIONS

This policy brief, based on the work of the European BUDDIE-PACK project (Horizon Europe), outlines the technical, health and functional requirements needed to standardise reusable plastic packaging. It highlights key challenges related to safety, sustainability and user acceptability, and proposes policy recommendations to support the development and uptake of these standards. In particular, it calls for the European Commission to mandate a European standardisation body to develop harmonised technical standards, which could then be formally endorsed through EU legal instruments—such as delegated acts under the PPWR—ensuring consistent implementation across Member States. This approach would facilitate integration into future European packaging regulations, support reuse deployment, and drive adoption by businesses and consumers.

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THE CHALLENGE

Establish a common European framework for the performance and verification of reusable plastic packaging intended for contact-sensitive applications by ensuring that such packaging:

- Maintains **functional integrity and health safety** throughout its lifecycle.
- Complies with existing **EU regulatory requirements** (Regulations EC 178/2002, EC 852/2004, EC 1935/2004 and EU 10/2011).
- Meets **consumer expectations**, including aesthetics and organoleptic properties.
- Relies on **harmonised and reproducible testing methods** across Member States.

WHY IT MATTERS

The European Union has included reuse targets in the packaging and packaging waste regulation (PPWR).

Reuse systems must meet safety, functional and economic requirements in order to become a credible alternative to single-use plastic packaging. The European Buddie-pack project, part of the Horizon Europe programme (Horizon-CL6-2021-Circbio-01), aims to develop systemic solutions for the reuse of plastic packaging in mass consumption applications by proposing, in particular, protocols for verifying the safety, integrity, and durability of reusable plastic packaging (RPP) intended for contact sensitive applications in order to support standardisation at European level. The recommendations made as part of the Buddie-pack project are designed to fit within the framework of the PPWR and to support its implementation with a view to contributing to the standardisation work required for the implementation of the PPWR by incorporating the work carried out within the project

POLICY RECOMMENDATIONS

1 POLICY RECOMMENDATION 1: ESTABLISH HARMONISED DESIGN REQUIREMENTS UNDER THE PPWR

ESTABLISH HARMONISED DESIGN REQUIREMENTS FOR REUSABLE PLASTIC PACKAGING UNDER THE PPWR

The European Commission should introduce **binding essential requirements (e.g. under Article 5 of the PPWR), to be specified and operationalised through delegated acts**, to ensure that reusable plastic packaging intended for contact-sensitive applications is designed for safe and efficient reuse.

These requirements should ensure that packaging:

- Is made of materials compliant with EU food contact legislation and suitable for repeated use.
- Is compatible with existing industrial production and reuse systems, including washing and logistics infrastructure.
- Is designed according to circular economy principles, notably by promoting mono-material solutions and limiting non-recyclable additives.
- Meets economic feasibility conditions, supporting large-scale adoption without disproportionate costs.
- Compliance should be demonstrated through conformity assessment procedures before placing products on the market.

INTRODUCE MINIMUM PERFORMANCE REQUIREMENTS FOR HYGIENE, SAFETY, AND DURABILITY

To guarantee safe reuse over time, the Commission should mandate harmonised performance criteria, supported by European standards. These should require that reusable packaging:

- **Is designed for effective industrial cleaning**, including features such as smooth surfaces, rounded edges, and adequate drainage.
- Maintains its **mechanical and chemical resistance** over multiple washing and reuse cycles.
- Preserves **functional integrity and health safety** throughout its lifecycle.

Verification should rely on **standardised testing protocols and certification schemes**, ensuring consistent enforcement across Member States.

INTEGRATE CONSUMER ACCEPTANCE CRITERIA INTO POLICY FRAMEWORKS

Policy measures should ensure that reusable packaging remains acceptable and attractive to users, as this is critical for reuse system uptake. Requirements should include that packaging:

- Maintains **adequate aesthetic and organoleptic quality** over repeated use.
- Is **easy to use**, including handling, opening, closing, and transport.
- Includes mandatory digital **traceability tools** (e.g. digital labels or QR codes) to ensure safety, transparency, while supporting system management.
- Allows for **clear identification or differentiation** (e.g. through colour or design) to reinforce user confidence.

These aspects could be integrated into essential requirements or supporting guidelines under the PPWR.

2 POLICY RECOMMENDATION 2: ESTABLISH EU REQUIREMENTS FOR ACCELERATED AGEING TESTING OF REUSABLE PLASTIC PACKAGING

The European Commission should introduce mandatory requirements under the PPWR, supported by harmonised standards (e.g. via CEN/CENELEC), to ensure that reusable plastic packaging is assessed under realistic end-of-life conditions. These requirements should ensure that:

- Packaging performance is evaluated using **accelerated ageing protocols simulating the full reuse lifecycle**, including storage, food contact, transport, and repeated industrial washing.
- Testing reflects **realistic worst-case conditions**, defined as the most severe but foreseeable conditions during normal use (e.g. highest temperatures, longest contact times, most aggressive authorised substances, and maximum reuse cycles).
- Protocols are **time-efficient yet representative of real conditions**, ensuring feasibility for industry uptake.

Compliance should be demonstrated through standardised testing protocols and third-party conformity assessment, to ensure consistent implementation across Member States.

Accelerated ageing testing should be recognised as a mandatory step to verify compliance, particularly to assess risks at end-of-life such as chemical migration, material degradation, and loss of hygienic performance.

3 POLICY RECOMMENDATION 3: INTRODUCE HARMONISED EU ASSESSMENT REQUIREMENTS FOR SAFETY, HYGIENE, AND FUNCTIONALITY

The required assessments should form part of a harmonised and transparent certification process, based on clearly defined and reproducible test methods. This process must be accessible to all market operators, through individual applications, and must be carried out by qualified laboratories, thereby ensuring equitable access and the comparability of results. Compliance is verified as part of the certification process, with possible supervision by the competent authorities. In the event of non-compliance, the packaging must not be authorised for its intended use, and corrective measures must be implemented before it is placed or returned to the market.

CHEMICAL SAFETY ASSESSMENT

Policy frameworks should require that:

- **Migration testing** is carried out after accelerated ageing, in line with existing EU legislation (e.g. EU Regulation 10/2011), to reflect worst-case exposure conditions.
- Manufacturers assess **non-intentionally added substances (NIAS)** using appropriate analytical methods, ensuring full chemical safety over time.
- Risks linked to reuse (e.g. contamination, residues from cleaning agents, misuse) are addressed through **validated testing approaches**, inspired by existing EU methodologies (e.g. for recycling processes). In particular, assessments should rely on challenge-test protocols inspired by EFSA guidance for recycling process validation, adapted to the specific conditions of reusable packaging systems. The potential release of microplastics is evaluated using harmonised protocols as they become available, building in particular on emerging evidence such as the Buddie-pack D5.4 deliverable on the database of microplastic properties and related modelling.

These requirements should be established as mandatory provisions under the PPWR, and supported by harmonised European standards (e.g. developed through CEN/Cenelec) to ensure consistent implementation. Compliance should be enforced through mandatory conformity assessment and documentation obligations.

MICROBIOLOGICAL ASSESSMENT

EU policy should require that:

- Industrial washing processes are validated to ensure effective decontamination over repeated reuse cycles.
- Cleaning protocols are verified under real-use conditions, ensuring the absence of pathogens and biofilms.

These requirements should be established under the PPWR as binding essential requirements, further specified through harmonised EU standards (e.g. developed via CEN/Cenelec) and formally operationalised via delegated acts, ensuring consistent implementation across Member States. Compliance should be ensured through certification schemes and periodic verification, aligned with hygiene regulations.

FUNCTIONALITY ASSESSMENT

To ensure usability and consumer acceptance, policy requirements should ensure that packaging:

- Maintains organoleptic neutrality (no transfer of taste, odour, or colour) over time.
- Preserves mechanical integrity and surface properties despite repeated use and washing.
- Meets minimum visual and quality criteria, ensuring it remains acceptable for consumers.

These criteria should be integrated into essential requirements and standardised testing frameworks.

4 POLICY RECOMMENDATION 4: SUPPORT MARKET UPTAKE THROUGH HARMONISATION, INCENTIVES, AND ENABLING MEASURES

To complement technical requirements, the EU and Member States should implement enabling policy measures.

GOVERNANCE AND STAKEHOLDER COORDINATION

- Recognise the key role of local operators (e.g. retailers, food service operators, site managers), who often determine whether reuse systems are implemented in practice
- Introduce incentives and clear frameworks to support their participation
- Encourage the establishment of multi-stakeholder reuse working groups at national and sectoral levels to:
 - Align value chain actors
 - Share best practices
 - Support implementation of standards.

ECONOMIC INSTRUMENTS AND INNOVATION SUPPORT

- Implement eco-modulation of extended producer responsibility (EPR) fees to reward reusable and durable packaging.
- Mobilise EU and national funding (e.g. Horizon Europe, Life, Cohesion Funds) to support:
 - Reuse infrastructure (collection, washing, logistics)
 - Development of durable and safe materials
- Encourage public-private partnerships to accelerate deployment.

DEPOSIT-RETURN SYSTEMS AND INFRASTRUCTURE

- Assess the introduction of mandatory or minimum requirements for deposit-return systems for reusable packaging under the PPWR.
- Require Member States to establish national frameworks aligned with EU criteria, ensuring interoperability.
- Ensure dedicated funding mechanisms to support infrastructure rollout.

CONSUMER ENGAGEMENT

- Require clear labelling and communication on safety and sustainability.
- Promote traceability tools (e.g. digital systems) that should (as far as possible) be invisible to the users so that they can benefit without raising concerns..

CONCLUSION

The large-scale deployment of reusable plastic packaging for contact-sensitive applications requires **a robust, harmonised, and enforceable EU framework.**

The Buddie-pack project provides a strong scientific and methodological foundation to support this transition. Building on these results, the European Commission is well-positioned to act by integrating reuse-specific requirements into existing policy instruments, in particular the PPWR (e.g. essential requirements under Article 5), as well as through standardisation mandates and secondary legislation.

To accelerate progress and reduce the threshold for action, policymakers should prioritise:

- **The introduction of harmonised design and assessment requirements for reusable packaging.**
- **The recognition of accelerated ageing and lifecycle testing as core compliance tools.**
- **The development of EU-wide standards and conformity assessment mechanisms.**
- **The mobilisation of targeted economic instruments and infrastructure support to enable scale-up.**

EVIDENCE AND CONTEXTS

PACKAGING DESIGN

INDUSTRIAL SPECIFICATIONS

- **Material choice:** Must comply with food-contact regulations, resist multiple washing cycles, refilling, trips, consumer/user usage, and be compatible with recycling guidelines (e.g., Recyclclass). rPET is currently the only recycled material approved for food contact; rPE and rPP possible for non-food or via EFSA-approved closed-loop systems.
- **Design for recyclability:** Mono-material preferred; avoid incompatible additives (e.g., carbon black).
- **Functional requirements:** Stackability, nestability, leak-proof lids, tamper-proof seals, transparency or opacity based on consumer acceptance and industry requirements.
- **Thermal resistance:** Materials must withstand washing temperatures, microwave/oven heating, refrigeration, and freezing.
- **Surface roughness:** Ra < 0.8 µm recommended for hygiene; avoid sharp angles (radius ≥ 6 mm).
- **Draining ability:** Design to prevent water retention after washing.
- **Mechanical resistance:** Must resist deformation and cracking under heat and handling.
- **Gaskets and sealing systems:** Must be easy to clean and resistant to detergents and temperature.
- **Labels:** Avoid permanent labels; use water-soluble adhesives to reduce cleaning complexity.

ECONOMIC OVERVIEW

- **Refill home care bottles:** Comparable cost to SUP after initial mould investment; PE and PET options with recycled content.
- **Ready-meal trays:** Significant cost increase due to thicker walls (2–3 mm vs. 0.5–1 mm), heavier weight (55–60 g vs. 5–20 g), and longer cycle times.
- **Skin pack for meat:** Higher cost driven by thicker trays and material choice (CPET, PP); estimated cost ~€0.10/tray.

SPECIFICATIONS FOR WASHING, SAFETY, AND QUALITY

- Must tolerate industrial washing protocols (pH 3–12, high temperature, detergents).
- Ensure hygiene compliance (HACCP), easy cleaning, and drying to prevent microbial growth.
- Avoid design features that trap residues; implement traceability (cycle count, previous contents).
- Ageing risks: UV exposure, chemical attack, and scratches can increase contamination risk; monitoring required.

DRIVERS OF CONSUMER/USER ACCEPTANCE (COM-B FRAMEWORK)

- **Opportunity:** Hygiene guarantee, microwave/oven compatibility, stackability, ease of use.
- **Motivation:** Aesthetic appeal, resistance to marks/discoloration, recyclability at end of life.
- **Capability:** Clear communication (QR codes, washable labels), ergonomic design, easy handling.

SOCIO-ECONOMIC BARRIERS

- **Manufacturing:** Higher material costs for catering trays, ready-meals, and meat packs.
- **Storage:** Increased space requirements; special conditions for hygiene.
- **Filling:** Adaptation of lines, staff training, safety tests.
- **Distribution:** Need for transport mutualization; new logistics for refill bottles.
- **Collection:** Return rate challenges; incentives/penalties may be needed.
- **Cleaning:** Externalization for some use cases; industrial washing centers require large volumes for breakeven.
- **End of life:** Loss and breakage rates impact cost-effectiveness.

ACCELERATED AGEING TESTS

- **Simulated aging up to 200 days.**

Three key environments: T (60 °C dry), TW (water), TWD (water + 1% detergent).

- **Worst-case ageing protocols.**

Simulated up to 50 cycles using Arrhenius-based accelerated conditions (high temperature, detergent washing).

Polyesters (PETg, cPET, PBT, Tritan) showed strong resistance; PP exhibited more chemical changes.

ASSESSMENT

CHEMICAL SAFETY ASSESSMENT

- **Overall and specific migration tests.**

All tested materials (PETg, cPET, PBT, PP, Tritan) remained within EU regulation limits - results depend on use conditions and cannot be generalised. [Regulation (EU) N°10/2011] after accelerated ageing and multiple reuse cycles.

- **Non-targeted chemical analysis:**

- PP trays (Knauf, Ausolan) contained high oligomer content and showed significant changes after ageing:
- Decrease in original additives (oligomers, phthalates, antioxidants).
- Formation of new compounds (oxidized antioxidants, fragrances, fatty alcohols) due to detergent sorption.
- No genotoxic substances detected among identified compounds; unidentified substances treated under TTC approach.

- **Barrier properties and contaminant absorption:**

- Polyesters absorbed fewer contaminants than PP.
- Washing efficiency varied: 10–57% decontamination, better on aged materials than new.
- Mit (biocide) was least absorbed and most easily removed.

- **Migration modelling:**

- Critical for low molecular weight substances (100–300 g/mol) due to high migration potential.
- Case-by-case thresholds required; universal 100 ppm indicator deemed insufficient.

- **Sniffing technology:**

- Developed for real-time detection of VOCs (20 key chemicals identified).
- Effective in distinguishing contamination states and monitoring cleaning performance.

- **Microplastic release:**

- Microplastic release during reuse depends strongly on polymer type and ageing behaviour.
- PP, Tritan and PBT showed very limited release, while cPET and PETg exhibit higher fragmentation after ageing due to degradation.
- Most detected particles were smaller than 50 µm, highlighting the need for sensitive assessment methods.
- Microplastic generation is not addressed in current European regulations, highlighting a regulatory gap for reuse systems.

MICROBIOLOGICAL ASSESSMENT

- Definition of standardised steps: pre-wash, wash, rinse, neutralisation, drying.
- Critical parameters: temperatures (50–85°C), contact time, pressure (0.8 bar), belt speed (1.8 m/min).
- HACCP criteria: ATP, TPC, pathogens (*Salmonella*, *Listeria*, *E. coli*, *Staphylococcus*, *Campylobacter*).
- Products: alkaline detergents + oxidising disinfectants, eco-labelled.

FUNCTIONALITY ASSESSMENT

- **Polyesters (PET, PBT, Tritan) show remarkable stability.**

- No significant physico-chemical changes after thermal aging, water immersion, or immersion with detergent.
- Only notable observation: occasional migration of additives (stearates) on PBT, without major impact on performance.
- Shore D hardness and surface energy remain stable or slightly improved (e.g., PETc: 75 → 80 under TWD).
- Oxygen and water vapor barriers preserved thanks to semi-crystalline structure and wall thickness.

- **Polyolefins (PP) more sensitive to aging.**

- Slow oxidation detected (IR peak at 1740 cm⁻¹), especially under water/detergent immersion.
- Migration of additives (CaSt₂ → NaSt) accelerated by detergent, causing mass loss and yellowing.
- Shore D hardness shows moderate decrease (76 → 64 under T/TW), but remains acceptable for reuse.
- Surface energy varies: ↑ under TW (38 dyn/cm), ↓ under TWD (32 dyn/cm), impacting cleanability.

- **Recycled polyethylene (rPE) for detergent bottles: performance confirmed.**

- Excellent chemical compatibility (no cracks, swelling, or leakage after 15 days at 60 °C).
- OTR stable (0.61 → 0.55–0.65 cm³/m²-day) and WVTR low (0.0051 → 0.0018–0.0047 g/m²-day) after 12 months simulated.
- Mechanical resistance maintained (σ_m ≈ 19.6–21.3 MPa; ε_m ≈ 6.3–9.8%).

REFERENCES

Deliverable 1.3: Technical and economic specifications (public)

Deliverable 5.1: Decontamination equipment and technologies (public)

Deliverable 5.2: Post-use functional properties of RPP with materials database (public)

Deliverable 5.3: Report on migration modelling, contaminants absorption and barrier evaluations (public)

Deliverable 5.5: Pilot line for cleaning of reusable packaging (sensitive)

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